

Tracking Ply Deformation during Thermoplastic Stamp Forming using Embedded Shape Sensor

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Background

Stamp forming process

Advantage

- ✓ High-rate
- ✓ High-quality
- ✓ Complex structures

Background

Depending on forming conditions, heated composite plate is not properly pressed against mold....

- ✓ Areas of wavy plies and inadequate pressurization occur
- ✓ Mechanical properties of manufactured parts are reduced.

Now, forming conditions set by trial and error based on observations after forming

New in-situ measurement technology is needed to measure deformation of each ply during forming

Objective

- ✓ Measure deformation of thermoplastic composites during stamp forming using shape sensor (originally for thermoset composites*)
- ✓ Investigate influence of forming parameters on deformation behavior

*S. Minakuchi, S. Niwa, N. Takeda. "Strip-Type Embeddable Shape Sensor Based on Fiber Optics for In Situ Composite Consolidation Monitoring" *Sensors* 22, no. 17: 6604 (2022)

*T. Tamagawa, Y. Mori, S. Minakuchi. "Consolidation mechanism of composite corners cured on convex and concave tools" *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 169, 107500 (2023)

Forming parameters to be investigated

Strip-type shape sensor

- ✓ Two optical fibers embedded in upper and lower surfaces of thin polyimide sheet
- ✓ When bended along sensor axis, different strain (bending strain) is induced in two optical fibers and sensor shape can be back-calculated
- ✓ Deformation can be measured by embedding in composite

Strip-type shape sensor

Curvature $\kappa = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{lower}} - \epsilon_{\text{upper}}}{2z_c}$,

- ✓ When this flexible sensor is embedded in composite part during lay-up, **sensor deforms with surrounding plies**
- ✓ By monitoring shape change of sensor, we can clarify dynamic deformation process during consolidation

Material and specimen

Unit: mm

UD prepreg

- ✓ CF/PA6 (T_m : 219°C)
- ✓ Thickness : 200 μ m
- ✓ Stacking sequence : $[0_{10}]$

Stamp forming process

1.Heating

2.Transferring

3.Pressing

Spring support

Mold

Thermoplastic composites laminate

Hand hot press

Measurement: sampling 10Hz, spatial resolution 0.65mm

Result

Time			
0.0s	1.0s	2.0s	3.0s
4.0s	5.0s	6.0s	

- ✓ Curvature increased in corners
- ✓ Left and right curvature peaks moved outward
 >>Contact point with mold moved outward as forming progressed.
- ✓ Curvature did not match mold shape >> Ply distortion

Movement of contact points outward

Effect of press speed

- ✓ When fast, curvature increased locally, and straight part remained unchanged (a)
- ✓ When slow, curvature increased over wide region, and straight part deformed once before returning to straight (b)

Due to viscoelasticity of melted thermoplastic composite, deformation varied with press speed.

Effect of spring support

Longitudinal spring force changed corner shape
and caused gradual forming

Conclusions

- ✓ In-situ deformation monitoring technique was developed for stamp forming
- ✓ Technology will be applied to stamp forming with closed molds with large-scale